

UNIT PLANNING FOR PRAGMATIC INSTRUCTION: EXPLORING GRATITUDE IN L2 SPEECH ACTS

*E'zoxonova Nasimaxon Esorxonovna,
Oriental universiteti Tillar-2 kafedrası katta o'qituvchisi*

Abstract. It is important to mention that while completing Unit lesson plan, there has been a number of steps that I have walked through. Ishihara and Cohen suggest that combination of common curriculum and potentially coordinating content with other courses are considered two crucial criteria for lesson planning in pragmatics. Considering this, it was a bit difficult to choose proper speech act for L2 learners in terms of pragmatics. Next, the lesson plan should be designed with appropriate activities and tasks to acquire pragmatic knowledge in target language. Finally, it should be more focused on authentic materials and technology which based activities in order to provide meaningful and effective lesson plan for L2 learners.

Keywords: speech acts, sociolinguistics, summative assessment, formative assessment, analytic and holistic rubrics.

According to J.L. Austin, speech acts are considered speakers' utterances that convey meaning and make listeners do specific things. Therefore, in Carla website, there are various types of speech acts and among them the speech act of "thanks" seems appropriately for my unit lesson plan. The reason is that in this speech act, it occurred several misunderstandings while expressing phrases of thanks in target language. There would be also misuse of language choice should be taken into account. As Eisenstein and Bodman noted that L1 sociolinguistic behaviors and second language grammatical and lexical restriction impact on students' production in proper pragmatic forms while conveying thanks in target language. That is why this very speech act was chosen for Unit lesson plan.

As for the activities, it can be considered the diversity of the tasks while designing lesson plan. To be more precise, it focuses to include communicative activities such as role-plays, dialogues, DCT or production skills like writing a letter, formal instructions and technology which based activities such as Kahoot, Padlet and Quizizz and patchwork included as well. Moreover, to raise students' awareness on pragmatics and compare cultural identity different you tube videos, audio recording and songs are provided considerably. All of these activities are addressed to develop unit lesson plan on pragmatics.

Obviously, there were some challenges while designing Unit lesson plan effectively such as the delivery of meaning of sentences to L2 learners. To be more particularly, as the learners are non-native, they cannot comprehend the real meaning of the sentence and do not know how to respond properly. As Norton noted that one of the significant matter is that enchanted a lot of instructors in L2 identity is the connection between classrooms and communities in the process of language acquisition. Therefore, in this lesson plan, choosing appropriate tasks in terms of pragmatics were a little bit challenging. The reason is that all of the tasks cannot be

expressed according to pragmatic norms and manners. However, it can be managed to select proper and meaningful tasks and exercises for this lesson plan.

Importantly, while designing lesson plan, it gives very valuable knowledge in terms of the speech act of thanks and its usage in L2. Moreover, I have come across the strategies of speech act; found out various activities how to implement in the classroom context and applying digital tools in terms of pragmatics. The steps of delivering activities, how to make up contrasting dialogues, identifying contextual factors and providing suitable formal instructions have given effective results to acquire knowledge regarding to pragmatics. While designing lesson plan, it is paid attention on assessing students' awareness on pragmatics. As Brown stated that assessment is necessary to drive students' learning. Therefore, it is applied different types of assessment based on the type of activities. For instance, for some tasks such as making up dialogues or role-plays formative assessment was chosen. Summative assessment was provided to check students' writing at the end of the lesson. Moreover, in order to assess students' performance properly and effectively analytic and holistic rubrics were delivered.

After receiving feedback from my peer, I have realized that it should be looked through the lesson plan attentively. This means that it should be looked through some activities attentively, expand the diversity of tasks and also including authentic materials to the lesson plan. Moreover, according to peer-review, it is emphasized to add more TESOL standards to enrich the productivity of the lesson plan. Including all of the feedbacks, there has been done a number of changes within the lesson plan.

As it can be mentioned above, broad range of resources are provided for this lesson plan. for example, Carla website or technology based educational platforms such as Kahoot, Padlet and Quizzes are used to deliver pragmatic knowledge effectively and productively. Besides that, you tube videos and songs are highly provided to identify cultural diversity and served as an authentic source in terms of pragmatics in L2.

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